

Electron Acceptors. Part IV¹: Electron Spin Resonance Spectral Studies of 2,3-Dicyano-1, 4-Naphthoquinone Radical²

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The radical anion of electron acceptor 2,3-dicyano-1,4-naphthoquinone (1) was conveniently generated by the action of sodium metal in THF and also by the electrolytic reduction in a MeCN-DME mixture. Analysis of the ESR spectra suggests the presence of four equivalent protons ($a_H = 0.19$ G.) and two equivalent nitrogen atoms ($a_N = 0.87$ G.). The theoretical values of the unpaired electron spin densities and the hyperfine coupling constants for the radical anion (1) were obtained by the applications of both HMO- and INDO methods and the results were correlated with the experimental values.

OUR interest in establishing the relationship between structure, photoelectrical behavior and free radical properties of molecular complexes led us to investigate the acceptor properties of 2,3-dicyano-1,4-naphthoquinone (1) and analogous 1,4-naphthoquinone pi-acids with aromatic hydrocarbon donors¹.

The interaction of suitable aromatic *n*-donors and alkali metal salts generate stable radical anion complexes of (1). The semiconductive properties and electronic spectra of some of these complexes have recently been reported^{3,4}. This report thus presents the esr spectral studies of radical anion (1) in solution. Appropriate theoretical support of the esr spectrum and of the observed proton and nitrogen hyperfine splittings obtained by the application of molecular orbital methods are also reported.

Experimental

2,3-dicyano-1,4-naphthoquinone (1) was purified by repeated crystallization from acetonitrile, m.p. 272°-273°.¹ Solvents: acetonitrile (MeCN) was purified by distillation from P₂O₅; tetrahydrofuran (THF) and dimethoxyethane (DME) were distilled from sodium-potassium alloy. The solvents were stored under vacuum and thoroughly degassed by freeze-pump-thaw cycle before use.

ESR spectra were recorded by using a Varian E-9 spectrometer system equipped with a 22 cm. electromagnet, a 100 KHz field modulation unit, an E232 dual purpose cavity and a Varian E101 microwave bridge.

All experiments were performed at room temperature and in degassed solutions. Radical anion (1) (10⁻³M solution) was generated by the action of sodium mirror in degassed THF solution. The spectrum showed only five unresolved lines of intensities 1 : 2 : 3 : 2 : 1 for two equivalent nitrogen atoms ($a_N = 0.90$ G.). Electrolytic reduction of (1) (10⁻³M

solution) was performed by using a specially designed electrolytic cell⁵, in 60% acetonitriledimethoxy ethane mixture containing 0.10M tetra-*n*-propyl ammonium perchlorate as ion carrier. Electrolysis was carried out between silver-silver perchlorate and mercury pool electrodes. A well resolved spectrum of (1) consisting of 18 of the expected 25 lines (Fig. 2a) was obtained. Analysis of the spectrum showed the presence of two equivalent nitrogen atoms of intensities 1 : 2 : 3 : 2 : 1 and $a_N = 0.87$ G. This was split further by four protons of intensities 1 : 4 : 6 : 4 : 1, and $a_H = 0.19$ G. The above spectrum was reconstructed by using an esr "spectrum simulation program"⁶ (Fig. 2b).

All numerical calculations were performed by using a CDC 6600 computer at the AFCRL computer center.

HMO and HMO-SCF Calculations of Spin Densities

(a) Methods :

The molecular orbital calculations of pi-electron spin densities of radical anion (1) were performed with the simple Huckel-MO method and HMO-SCF method using the ω technique^{7a,b}.

For the hetero atoms in (1) several coulomb and resonance integrals were required. The empirical parameters associated with the coulomb integrals (α_X) and resonance integrals (β_{CX}) are defined as $\alpha_X = \alpha_C + h_X \beta_{CC}$ and $\beta_{CX} = k_{CX} \beta_{CC}$ for the hetero atoms X and for the C-X bonds respectively, h_X and k_{CX} being the empirical parameters as defined above (X = O, N). The ranges of the above parameters were kept within the limits of the suggested⁸ and most frequently used values⁹. For the oxygen of the carbonyl functions of (1) the empirical parameters $h_O = 1.20$ and $k_{CO} = 1.55$ were used for all calculations and the corresponding parameters for

nitrogen atoms in the cyano-groups (h_N and k_{CN}) were varied between 0.5 to 1.50β .

Calculations of spin densities (ρ_i) performed by using simple Huckel approximations (SHMO) involved computing orbital coefficients from a Huckel matrix^{7a}. To a first approximation the spin density (ρ_r) at atom 'r' is defined as $\rho_r = C_{0,r}^2$, where $C_{0,r}$ are the coefficients of the atomic orbitals in the MO containing the unpaired electron.

For the HMO-SCF method using the ω -technique^{7b,10} the coulomb integrals were expressed as $\alpha_r = \alpha_c + \omega(1 - q_r)\beta$, where q_r is the original charge density obtained from the SHMO-method and ω is a constant taken as 1.4. Calculations were continued until the self consistency of the charge densities " q_r " were achieved. From the HMO-SCF method new sets of spin densities were obtained.

The modifications of SHMO and HMO-SCF spin densities were performed following McLachlan's procedure^{11a,b}, which in terms of HMO-quantities were obtained by using equation 1 :

$$\rho'_r = C_{0,r}^2 - \lambda \sum_s C_{0,s}^2 \pi_{r,s} \quad \dots (1)$$

Here, ρ'_r is the corrected spin density for atom 'r', C_{ij} 's are the coefficients of the corrected atomic orbital wave functions containing the unpaired electron, $\pi_{r,s}$ are the atom-atom polarizabilities and λ is an empirical constant given the value 1.2β .

For HMO-SCF calculations the resonance integrals were not changed ($\beta = 1.0$), and for hetero atoms, parameter $k_{CN} = 1.50\beta$ was used. The newly derived coefficients (C_{ij}) were used for the calculation of HMO-SCF spin densities. ω -McLachlan spin densities were obtained by using equation 1 and the coefficients (C_{ij}) and $\pi_{r,s}$ which were derived from the HMO-SCF method.

(b) Calculation of spin densities :

The experimental "estimates" of proton (ρ_H) and nitrogen (ρ_N) spin densities were first obtained from the ratios of experimental hyperfine coupling constants a_H and a_N with the proportionality constants $Q_{CH} = 23.7$ G, and $Q'_N = 11.0$ G for protons and for nitrogens respectively. Calculations of spin densities were performed to achieve these 'estimates' by adjusting the values of empirical parameters h_N and k_{CN} during calculations.

It is evident from Table 1 that a single set of empirical parameters h_N and k_{CN} could not be used to provide acceptable proton spin densities (ρ_H) either from SHMO or from McLachlan methods. In the range of h_N and k_{CN} values examined, the relative spin density variations at para (ρ_{H^1}) and ortho (ρ_{H^2}) positions are observed in all cases, with $\rho_{H^1} > \rho_{H^2}$. With the values of parameters $k_{CN} > h_N$ the calculated SHMO spin densities were found to be too high, whereas corresponding values obtained from the McLachlan method were within the range of "experimental estimate". Alternatively, with the parameters $h_N \geq k_{CN}$, calculated SHMO spin densities were within the expected range, and McLachlan spin densities especially for the ortho-protons (ρ_{H^2}) were quite low. The McLachlan spin density with parameters $h_N = k_{CN} = 1.50$, however, showed almost equivalent values for ortho and para-protons. Spin densities obtained from the HMO-SCF method showed almost zero spin densities for all protons.

Calculated nitrogen spin densities (ρ_N) from SHMO and McLachlan methods were found to be sensitive to the value of parameter k_{CN} . For both SHMO and McLachlan spin densities, plots of calculated ρ_N against k_{CN} showed convergence of ρ_N at $k_{CN} = 1.50$, with the values of h_N ranging between 0.5 to 1.50β .

From SHMO, HMO-SCF and McLachlan methods consistent values of ρ_N and $\rho_{C'}$ were obtained. The calculated spin densities of all 4 sources are presented in Table 2, columns 1 through 4.

TABLE 1—CALCULATED PROTON SPINDENSITIES (ρ) AND HYPERFINE COUPLING CONSTANTS ($a_H G$) FOR (1)

($h_0 = 1.20$, $k_{CO} = 1.55$)

Parameters		SHMO-Method				McLachlan Method (Eq. 1)			
h_N	k_{CN}	ρ_1	ρ_2	a_{H^1}	a_{H^2}	ρ_1	ρ	a_{H^1}	a_{H^2}
0.5	1.0	0.0138	0.0126	0.33	0.30	0.0086	0.0092	0.20	0.22
0.8	0.8	0.0090	0.0060	0.21	0.14	0.0058	0.0032	0.13	0.07
0.8	1.2	0.0145	0.0127	0.34	0.30	0.0092	0.0090	0.22	0.21
1.0	1.0	0.0107	0.0077	0.25	0.18	0.0071	0.0045	0.16	0.10
1.0	1.2	0.0133	0.0108	0.31	0.25	0.0086	0.0072	0.20	0.17
1.2	1.0	0.0099	0.0066	0.23	0.15	-0.0065	0.0034	0.15	0.08
1.5	1.0	0.0091	0.0055	0.21	0.13	0.0060	0.0023	0.14	0.05
1.5	1.5	0.0140	0.0170	0.34	0.40	0.0091	0.0080	0.21	0.19

TABLE 2—CALCULATED NITROGEN SPIN DENSITIES (ρ_N) AND HYPERFINE COUPLING CONSTANTS a_H (G.)

($h_0 = 1.20$; $k_{CO} = 1.55$; $k_{CN} = 1.50$)

h_N	1 SHMO			2 McLachlan			3 HMO-SCF			4 ω -McLachlan Spindensity		
	ρ_N	$\rho_{C'}$	$a_N^{(1)}$	ρ_N	$\rho_{C'}$	$a_N^{(1)}$	ρ_N	$\rho_{C'}$	$a_N^{(2,3a)}$	ρ_N	$\rho_{C'}$	$a_N^{(2,3b)}$
0.50	0.0702	0.0088	0.77	0.0820	-0.0134	0.90	0.0450	0.0100	0.72	0.0507	-0.0031	0.94
0.80	0.0730	0.0203	0.80	0.0822	0.0010	0.90	0.0453	0.0100	0.86	0.0510	-0.0021	0.93
1.00	0.0735	0.0304	0.81	0.0800	0.0140	0.88	0.0455	0.0104	0.73	0.0511	-0.0015	0.93
1.20	0.0731	0.0420	0.80	0.0755	0.0300	0.83	0.0457	0.0110	0.72	0.0512	-0.0010	0.93
1.50	0.0705	0.0607	0.77	0.0673	0.0533	0.74	0.0460	0.0120	0.72	0.0512	0.0000	0.93

1) a_N calculated by using Eq. 3.

2) a_N calculated by using Eq. 2.

3) Calculated by using the relation $a_N = K\rho_N$, $K = 18.5G$. (Eq. 4, 5, ref. 13).

a) $a_N = 0.83$ to 0.85 G.

b) $a_N = 0.94$ G.

(c) Calculation of a_H :

Experimentally measured proton coupling constants were compared with those calculated from McConnell's equation¹², $a_H = Q_{CH} \rho_i$, where a_H is the splitting due to the proton, ρ_i is the spin density on the adjacent carbon atom and Q_{CH} is the interaction of the pi-electron with the C-H sigma bond. Various values of Q_{CH} have been proposed; however for anion radical (1) a value of $Q_{CH} = 23.7$ G¹³ was used. Calculated a_H^1 and a_H^2 for para and ortho-protons respectively are presented in Table 1, and are compared with the experimentally measured values.

(d) Calculation of a_N :

The theories of hyperfine couplings suggest that splittings due to C¹³ and N¹⁴ atoms depend not only on the spin densities on these nuclei alone but also on the neighbouring atoms (C') attached to them^{14,15,16}. For the nitrogen atom in aromatic nitrile, where there is an unshared pair of electrons in the sp-orbital, a modified Karplus-Fraenkel relation¹⁷ was developed to accommodate the contributions of 1-s electron polarization and 2-s polarization arising from the unshared pair of electrons on the nitrogen splitting¹³. In a simplified expression the experimentally measured a_N is thus related to the spin densities of nitrogen (ρ_N) and neighbouring carbon ($\rho_{C'}$) attached to the nitrogen atom of nitrile in equation (2)^{15,18}, where Q_1 and Q_2 are chosen constants.

$$a_N = Q_1\rho_N - Q_2\sum\rho_{C'} \quad \dots (2)$$

For nitrogens in aromatic nitriles and in heterocyclic systems Fraenkel^{13,19} observed that the contribution of a sigma-pi interaction parameter due to neighbouring carbon ($Q_{C'N}^N$) to a_N is small, and the sign of this parameter is most probably negative. Following this analogy it seems appropriate that Q_2

should be negative. Further, if the magnitude of the contribution from C' to a_N is small then the nitrile nitrogen splitting could be expressed by equation (3), where a_N is proportional to the spin density of nitrogen alone, and Q_N' is the corresponding σ - π parameter. For most nitrogen heterocyclic radicals, Eq. (3) has been found to work well^{17,20}.

$$a_N = Q_N' \rho_N \quad \dots (3)$$

Nitrogen hyperfine coupling constants (a_N) of (1) were obtained from equation (2) and from equation (3) by using the calculated spin densities presented in Table 2. For these calculations the values of proportionality constants $Q_1 = 18.0$, $Q_2 = 9.0$ and $Q_N' = 11.0$ G²¹ were used. Calculated coupling constants (a_N) are presented in Table 2, columns 1 through 4.

From SHMO and McLachlan spin densities the calculated a_N ranged between 0.74 to 0.90 G. With parameter h_N set at 0.8 and 1.0, the calculated values were 0.80 G (SHMO) and 0.88 G (McLachlan). Values of a_N derived from equation (2) and ρ_N and $\rho_{C'}$ from SHMO and McLachlan methods were found to be too high. However, equation (2) seems to give more acceptable values of a_N rather than equation (3), with the ρ_N and $\rho_{C'}$ obtained from HMO-SCF and ω -McLachlan methods. Calculated a_N from the HMO-SCF method ranged between 0.72 to 0.86 G. On the other hand a_N calculated by the ω -McLachlan method did not show any appreciable variations (≈ 0.93 G).

In Table 2 the calculated a_N from equation (2) and equation (3) are compared with the values obtained by using Fraenkel's equation.¹³ The calculated a_N in this case ranged between 0.83 to 0.85 G with the spin densities determined by the HMO-SCF method and was 0.94 G when the ω -McLachlan method was used.

Calculation of a_H and a_N by the INDO-Method:

From the results presented above it is evident that the calculated values of a_H and a_N from empirical methods are in good agreement with the experimental values. However, fitting the results by varying the parameters k_N and k_{CN} , and proportionality constants (Q) are in some respect an unsatisfactory procedure. Thus an independent check of the results by using the semi-empirical all valence INDO-method of Pople²² is justified here. Although INDO-parameters are not chosen independently of esr considerations, the method has been successful for a wide variety of free radicals²³.

For this purpose a modified CNDO-INDO program²⁴ was used. The anion radical (1) was assumed to be planar; bond angles and bond lengths derived from the X-ray crystal structure of 1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives²⁵ were used for the calculation of cartesian co-ordinates²⁵ (Fig. 1).

2,3-Dicyano-1,4-Naphthoquinone
 All bond angles 120°
 All aromatic $c-c$ bonds $1.39\text{\AA}$
 Bond 2-3, 9-10 = $1.39\text{\AA}$
 Bonds 1-2 = 3-4 = 1-9 = 4-10 = $1.45\text{\AA}$
 Bonds 2-13 = 3-14 = $1.36\text{\AA}$
 Bonds 13-15 = 14-16 = $1.16\text{\AA}$
 Bonds 1-11 = 4-12 = $1.21\text{\AA}$
 All C-H bonds = $1.08\text{\AA}$

Fig. 1.

To obtain maximum convergence of the SCF-cycle a damping factor (δ) was introduced into the program²⁷. A value of $\delta = 0.6$ or 0.7 proved satisfactory for this calculation. A variation of less than 10^{-5} eV in the energy was obtained compared to 10^{-2} eV obtained without the damping factor. The calculated a_H values were obtained by using the proportionality constant derived by Pople²². For a_N , proportionality constants derived by Pople and by Hirst²⁸ were used.

The calculated spin densities, hyperfine coupling constants and electronic charges of (1) from the INDO method are presented in Table 3. The overall agreement of the calculated a_H and a_N with the experimental values are quite good. Results clearly show the inequivalency of ortho (18, 19)- and para

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Fig. 2.

(17, 20)-protons and thus adequately support the observations made by HMO-methods. Further, the values of the calculated a_H for the protons indicate the inductive effects of nitrile substituents at 2,3 positions of naphthoquinone π system. The nitrogen hyperfine couplings (a_N) were found to vary between 0.83 to 0.96 G; however, a better correlation coefficient derived from a large number of nitrogen heterocyclic radicals could very well improve these values. The C^{13} and O^{17} couplings presented in Table 3 are not supported by any experimental data, although these calculated values along with the value of a_N indicate that the unpaired electron in (1) is more or less localized in the ring A of the anion radical (1).

TABLE 3—CALCULATED HYPERFINE COUPLING CONSTANTS OF (1) FROM INDO METHOD

Atom (No.)	Charge (Units of Electrons)	s-Orbital Spindensity	Hyperfine Coupling Constants (a)
C(1)	+0.2445	-0.0080	(-) 6.54
C(2)	-0.0984	0.0060	4.89
C(5)	+0.0241	-0.0009	(-) 0.697
C(6)	+0.0046	0.0002	0.16
C(9)	-0.0310	0.0009	0.70
C(13)	+0.1634	-0.0045	(-) 3.66
N(15)	-0.3148	0.0025	0.96 ^(a) 0.83 ^(b)
O(11)	-0.4100	0.0089	7.95
H(17)	-0.0337	0.0005	0.29
H(18)	-0.0517	-0.0001	(-) 0.06

Correlation Coefficient derived by (a) Pople²³, (b) Hirst²⁸.

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